

**COMPARATIVE STUDY OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND
JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL
TEACHERS****Suhara P Muhammdkutty***Research Scholar,**Gandhi Shikshan Bhavan's Smt. Surajba College of Education,**Mumbai University, Maharashtra***Dr. Frances Vaidya***Associate Professor,**Gandhi Shikshan Bhavan's Smt. Surajba College of Education,**Mumbai University, Maharashtra***Abstract**

Teacher is the most vital single factor of influence in the system of education. It is the teacher who matters most as far as the quality of education is concerned. The educational process is governed by the extent of receptivity and initiative. The well-equipped teacher is supreme in education. At all times the teacher is the pivot in the system of education. This is especially the case in a period of basic change' and reorientation. The study aimed at finding the difference between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. of secondary school teachers on the bases of gender and types school board. The data was descriptively and inferentially analyzed. Emotional intelligence scale was constructed by Dr. Ekta Sharma and. used for the purpose of the study with the necessary permission. Job satisfaction scale was constructed by the researcher. 600 secondary school teachers were selected from different SSC and CBSE schools of Raigad district. Descriptive analysis and Anova i.e. 't' test done for analysis. . The descriptive analysis revealed that for the mean score of Emotional Intelligence the male Secondary school teachers are marginally higher than the female Secondary school teachers. Similarly the SSC teachers are marginally higher than the CBSE school teachers when we

compare the mean score. In the inferential analysis, the 't' test revealed that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence on the bases of gender and types of school board.. For job satisfaction the t test revealed that there is no significant difference on the bases of gender. However there is a significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teacher on the bases of types of school board. The SSC school teachers are moderately higher than the CBSE secondary school teachers.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, Job Satisfaction, Education, Teacher, Female and Male, Type of School Boards, Secondary school teaches.

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Introduction

Teacher is an educational leader and decision maker, who directly affects and indirectly influences the students. It is the responsibility of the teacher to guide and inspire students, to enrich his disciples and inculcate values". Further, the teacher has to discharge various administrative duties of the school as and when required, viz. frame timetable, arrange school functions, conduct examinations and co-curricular activities, maintain office records and so on. The task of a teacher is quite challenging. It is far more difficult than it was a few decades ago. To maintain high standard of education quality there are chances that it will take a toll on teacher's emotional intelligence in order to adjust and cope up new challenges. Affected emotional intelligence further leads to job satisfaction in school teachers.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence is a master aptitude a capacity that profoundly affects all other abilities either facilitating or interfering with them. Variety of words and phrases have been used to define the factors which govern Emotional Intelligence. The ability get along with people and situation. A positive and protective attitude towards all aspects of life. The ability to command respect by building relationship. There are three major components to Emotional Intelligence motivating oneself, motivating others and empathizing with others which clearly describe the functional areas which determine the Emotional Intelligence of a person. A teacher who has a good emotional intelligence well with satisfied her job.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the result of various attitudes possessed by an employee. In a narrow sense, their attitudes are related to the job and are concerned with such specific factors as wages, supervision, steadiness of employment, conditions of work, opportunities for advancement, recognition of ability, fair evaluation of work, social relations on the job, prompt settlement of grievances, fair evaluation of work, social relations on the job, prompt settlement of grievances, fair treatment by employer, and other similar items. However, other aspects such as employee's age, health, temperament, desires and level of aspirations are also important. Further his family relationships social status, recreational outlets, activities organisations like labour, political or social, contribute ultimately to job satisfaction. Through the literature review of emotional intelligence and job satisfaction suggests that teaching profession is important part of teachers.

Review of Related Literature

Review of related literature is one of the essential steps for the conduct of research study. It gives the investigator an understanding of the previous work that has been done. The importance of the review of related literature cannot be denied in any research. It is the crucial aspect of the study and the time spent on such a survey helps the investigator in avoiding duplication of work. It provide theories, ideas, explanations or hypotheses in formulating the problems and contribute to the general scholarship of the investigator. This literature can be in the form of books, government publications, educational reports, educational abstracts, research journals etc.

Valente, S (2020) the role of the teacher's emotional intelligence for efficacy and classroom management. In recent years, several studies have revealed multiple benefits of teachers' emotional intelligence (EI) concerning their professional performance, regarding teaching and learning process, students' school performance, job satisfaction, reduction of stress and burnout, and the importance of interpersonal relationships at school. the aim of this study was twofold: to examine the relationship between teacher's EI capacities, teacher efficacy, and classroom management effectiveness, and to analyze the relationship between teacher's characteristics (gender) and professional background (service time).

Sharma (2017) The present research aims to determine the mediating role of Job satisfaction

between the leader's emotional intelligence and Organizational Engagement of teachers and also the relation of emotional intelligence of the group leaders with Employee Job Satisfaction and Organizational Engagement. The survey is conducted using the survey questionnaire specially designed for the purpose of exploring the relation between emotional intelligence, Job satisfaction and Organizational engagement. Questionnaires were distributed to 200 teachers working in different educational institutions in Delhi-NCR Region and 128 questions were analyzed. A 36-questions survey, which incorporates the parts of Emotional intelligence, job satisfaction and Organizational Engagement was completed to search the relationship among these factors. Some essential questions about personal details likewise included. To analyze the data, multiple regression analysis was used. It was found Job Satisfaction mediates significantly between leader's Emotional Intelligence and organizational Engagement.

Aduko, Akaribo William 2020) Job Satisfaction and Teacher Retention in Selected Senior High School in Ghana The study investigated into job satisfaction and teacher retention. Fifty teachers who were made up of 36 males and 14 females were randomly sampled. Questionnaire was used in the data collection. A good number of the teachers agreed to factors such as salary, accommodation and administrative support contributing to job satisfaction. The second research question was to find out in what ways job dissatisfaction affected teachers' performance in Zuarungu Senior High School.

ytac T (2020) The effects of working in public or private schools on job satisfaction of teachers in turkey: A meta-analysis study Purpose: The main problem of this study is to investigate whether the school type (private/public) has any effects on job satisfaction of teachers or not to reveal the effects of the school type on job satisfaction of teachers in Turkey. According to the results of this research, in accordance with the random effects model a statistically significant medium level of effect size was detected in favour of teachers working in private schools concerning the school type variable. As a result of the conducted moderator analysis, it was determined that the effect sizes of the studies varied by the grade of education, and the place of research Effect sizes of the studies did not differ significantly publication type), the title of the teacher and the scale Implications for Research and Practice: In the context of this meta-analysis study, the findings suggest that qualitative and quantitative studies

discussing which factors are effective in high job satisfaction of teachers working in private schools should be carried out.

Aim of the Study

The study aimed at finding the difference between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the bases of gender and types school board

Objectives of the Study

- To study the difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male Secondary School Teachers.
- To study the difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.
- To study the difference in the Job Satisfaction of Secondary School teachers on the basis of gender namely Female and Male Secondary School teachers.
- To study the difference in the Job Satisfaction of Secondary School teachers on the basis of board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Hypothesis of the Study

- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely Female and Male secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.
- There is no significant difference in the Job Satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender namely Female and Male secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant difference in the Job Satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Delimitation of the Study

- The study was conducted in SSC board and CBSE board schools of Raigad only.
- The study was limited to 600 secondary school teachers.

Research Methodology

Methodology of the Study

The study aimed at finding the difference between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the bases of gender and types school board. The data was descriptively and inferentially analyzed.

Methods and Techniques of Sampling

A researcher adopts a suitable sampling technique so that the sample drawn makes a good representation of the entire population. In the present study, the sample will be consisting of approximately 600 teachers from SSC and CBSE schools. Only qualified Secondary school teachers.

In the present study, a two stage sampling procedure is used where at the first stage the schools were selected and at the second stage teachers were selected. In the first stage of sampling, the researcher initially collected the list of the schools. For the purpose of the study the researcher selected the schools on the basis of their types namely CBSE and SSC. Thus the researcher used stratified random sampling for selecting the school. The simple random sampling is also used for selecting the schools in each stratum. At the second stage the teachers were selected. The simple random sampling technique was used to select teachers. The researcher met the secondary school teachers herself and most of them were willing to fill in the tool and so it can be said that the incidental sampling technique was used.

The total sample consisted of 600 secondary school teachers of which there were 376 teachers from CBSE schools and 224 teachers from SSC schools of Raigad District, who were currently employed in their respective schools. Where the medium of instruction is English.

Tool Used

- The researcher used a readymade tool for Emotional Intelligence constructed by Prasad Corporation (New Delhi) that is ready made tool.
- Job satisfaction tool constructed by researcher for the purpose of the study.

Data for this study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The items are were structured using modified 4 points Likert scale of strongly agreed (SA) = 4 point, agreed (A) =3 points, disagreed (D) = 2 points and strongly disagreed (SD) = 1 points. The reverse is the case for a negative statement.

The draft of the tool was given to eight experts from the faculty of education of the Mumbai University, for face and content validation. Base on the comments, suggestions and inputs made by these experts, the tool was further improved. In order to ascertain the tool reliability, a pilot study was conducted.

Procedure

After administering the tools on the sample, the scoring was done as per the scoring system.

Data Analysis

Data collected for the main study was analysis by descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. To find out the difference between variables Anova i.e. 't' test done for analysis.

Result

Descriptive Analysis For Emotional Intelligence

	Sample size	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	310	155.01	158	162	6.423	0.390	1.732
Male	290	155.51	157	162	6.859	0.870	-0.753
SSC Board	224	155.61	158	162	5.967	1.045	-1.590
CBSE Board	376	155.43	158	162	6.458	0.584	-0.260

Interpretation: The mean score of Emotional Intelligence the male Secondary school teachers are marginally higher than the female Secondary school teachers. Similarly the SSC teachers are marginally higher than the CBSE school teachers when we compare the mean score.

Descriptive Analysis For Job Satisfaction

	Sample size	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	310	138.94	141	144	7.560	0.904	-0.429
Male	290	138.75	140	142	8.522	2.714	0.271
SSC Board	224	140.37	140	144	8.072	1.688	-0.177
CBSE Board	376	139.37	140	142	8.242	3.148	0.181

Interpretation: The mean value of Job satisfaction indicates that job satisfaction of Female Secondary school teachers is slightly higher as compare to male secondary school teachers. Similarly the job satisfaction of SSC secondary school teachers is higher as compared to CBSE board school teachers.

Inferential Analysis

- **For Hypothesis 1** There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Gender namely male and female secondary school teachers.

Table 1:

Group	N	Mean	SD	't' value	l.o.s	Result
Female	310	156.05	6.610	1.957	0.05	Accepted
Male	290	155.01	6.423			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of female , male teachers is 1.957 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of female and male teachers of secondary school.

Conclusion: There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender. The mean value indicates that the female teachers are more emotional intelligence than the male teachers.

Discussion: The female teachers are highest in emotional intelligence when compared to male teachers. There might be conducive environment which brings in discussion regarding various professional, academic problems of the organization. The open dialogue among all female staff members develops good communication skills, enthusiasm. The solving problems collectively provide an opportunity to visualize problem from different angles which help in the development of decision making ability.

- **For Hypothesis 2** There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School teachers on the basis of Board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Table 2

Board	N	Mean	SD	't' value	l.o.s	Result
CBSE	376	155.51	6.859	0.189	0.05	Accepted
SSC	224	155.61	5.967			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of SSC and CBSE teachers is 0.189 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of CBSE and SSC teachers of secondary school.

Conclusion: There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers on the basis of Board. There is no difference in their mean value.

Discussion: The CBSE and SSC board secondary school teacher's emotional intelligence are near about the same. Emotional intelligence as the awareness and ability to do and handle situations emotionally rather than the intellectually. Emotional awareness and ability to handle feelings rather than the I.Q to determine the success and happiness in all walks of life. Dimensions of emotional intelligence are self-awareness, empathy, emotional stability and managing relations.

- **For Hypothesis 3** There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender namely male and female secondary school teachers.

Table 3

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' value	l.o.s	Result
Female	310	139.74	9.088	1.162	0.05	Accepted
Male	290	138.94	7.560			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of female, male teachers 1.162 which is greater than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of female and male teachers of secondary school.

Conclusion: There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender. The mean value indicates that the female teachers are more satisfied their job when compared to male teachers.

Discussion: The female teachers are more satisfied of the job of the secondary school teachers with respect to pay, promotion, supervision and work schedule. Job satisfaction in this study refers to the satisfaction of job of the secondary school teachers.

- **For Hypothesis 4** There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of board namely SSC and CBSE school boards.

Table 4:

Board	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Loss	Result
CBSE	376	138.75	8.522	2.325	0.05	Rejected
SSC	224	140.37	8.072			

Interpretation of 't'

The t value of CBSE, SSC teachers is 2.325 which is less than the tabulated value at 0.05 level. This implies that there is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of female and male teachers of secondary school.

Conclusion: There is a significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers on the basis of board.

Discussion: The SSC board teachers are more satisfied their job on the bases of pay, promotion, work schedule and supervision. CBSE teachers are not satisfied their work schedule, supervision and pay. SSC board teachers receiving good pay scale when compared to CBSE secondary school teachers.

Conclusion

In the inferential analysis, the 't' test revealed that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence on the bases of gender and types of school board.. For job satisfaction the t test revealed that there is no significant difference on the bases of gender. However there is a significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teacher on the bases of types of school board. The SSC school teachers are moderately higher than the CBSE

secondary school teachers. Therefore emotional intelligence and job satisfaction plays an important role for teachers.

Suggestions

- All the respondents to this survey belonged to Secondary School teachers. If this study were to be conducted again, the researcher would suggest including the teachers working at different level of educations like primary, secondary and tertiary.
- The study could also include Municipal schools, ICICI and the IB boards too. The rating scale can also be altered, so that the secondary school students could be the respondent. A comparative study is also recommended between the types of schools and board affiliations.

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